

HEALTH CARE PROVIDERS WORKING IN CRITICAL CARE UNITS; SEPARATION FROM FAMILY AND ITS IMPACT ON SOCIAL LIFE AT PEOPLES MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITAL NAWABSHAH, SINDH, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: Health care provider (HCP) working in the critical care units bearing the double burden of responsibilities of critical units and home. This burden impact on the personal life of HCP. These increase the family separation, and also cause the physical and emotion burnout. These healthcare settings require them to stay alert any time and long hours duties night duties and during emergencies overtime duties because they manage and face unexpected or unpredictable emergencies and they make life saving conditions under constant pressure erratic crisis and make life saving decisions under ongoing tension.

Methodology: This study was analytical cross-sectional study, in which strata sampling technique was used, and conducted from August to October 2025, in the critical care department of Peoples Medical College Hospital Nawabshah.

Results: The majority (73.3%) of participants experienced separation from family due to the working in the critical care units. Moreover, large number of participants reported that missing important family events, (63.0%) limited quality time with family, and reduced participation in social gatherings (68.4%). And feelings of stress, guilt (71.7%), and also (76.0%) social isolation were commonly reported particularly among females and those working in evening and night shifts. However, several other factors impact on family and social life.

Conclusion: This study concluded to assess the impact of critical care units on social life, and identified those factors which impact on social life, and compare the difference in family separation between male and female of healthcare providers at PMCH Nawabshah.

Introduction: Health care providers those are working in critical care units they are facing many of challenges and problems at the emergencies

wards the intensive care unit (ICU) can be an extremely distressing experience, leading to physical and psychological symptoms for both

patients and their families (1). Work-family conflict among physicians and nurses has many adverse consequences like reduced work engagement and impaired their well-being.(2).The negative psychosocial impacts of these policies that the full breadth of impacts on patients, families, and healthcare professionals are not fully understood. (3) The inter professional ICU team, social workers can function as trauma informed systems experts, coordinating and facilitating supports to help patients and families cope with hospitalization(4) the Physicians reported negative changes to daily workflow and ability to provide medical care in the absence of family visitors (5)The overtime hours worked by nurses, and employed more expert-level clinical nurses and combined nursing assistant/health unit coordinator positions, than lower performing units.(6) It also causes many of dilemmas so they face these challenges also but they are must to be ready to handle these emergencies at any time of the movement. Without seeing their problems, they perform their long hour's duties in stressful critical care units. And carry a heavy work load and separation from their families. But these challenges cause them psychological problems social life disturbance and include emotional and personal life stress. But they continue the care of patients those are in critical ill or critical conditions with honestly and faithfulness often ignoring their emotional pain and their personal struggles. In the critical care environment conflict may occur between all stakeholders mainly between the patient/family and the ICU team or/and between members of the healthcare team (7). Negative personal and professional consequences result from work-life imbalance including increased anxiety, depression, burnout, and decreased productivity of the work and job demands(8). The healthcare providers those are suffering from disconnection from their loved ones they feel more alones (9). These challenges cause withdraw from work job satisfaction are effected even some resign their jobs for their families and reducing the burden of the workload. These results are very important some countries like Pakistan. Where social identity is very

important depend on family connections and their community support. The aim of study was to critically examine the extent of family separation experienced by health care providers working in critical care units and to evaluate its impact on their social functioning, emotional well-being and overall quality of life within the context of demanding clinical environment.

Objectives of study: This study assessed the impact of critical care units on health care providers on social life, identified those factors which impact on social life of healthcare providers, and compared the difference in family separation between male staff and female staff those are working at critical care units at Peoples Medical Hospital Nawabshah, Sindh, Pakistan

Material & Methods: This study was analytical cross-sectional study, which is conducted from August to October 2026 at Collage of Nursing, Female Nawabshah. The Strata sampling technique was used. The sample size was determined using the Rao-Soft sample size calculator at a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, 50% response distribution, and a target population 350 Nurses and Doctors. The required sample size was calculated as 184 nurses and doctors.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Nursing and doctors Staff at least one year experience in critical care units.
2. Nurses, doctors, and paramedics were working in critical care units ICU, CCU, TRAMA.
3. Both Gender Male, and Female.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Nurses and doctors who were on leave or resigned and transferred less than 1 year from the duty area.
2. Nurses and doctors those were not working in critical care units and not working in hospital or clinical setting areas.

Tools for Data Collection: A data was collected by a structured questionnaire composed of four

sections: (A) Demographics (B) Work characteristics (shift patterns, duty hours) (C) Family Separation Scale (questions on missed events, daily time with family) (D) Social Life Scale (participation in social events, friendships for giving social support). The questionnaire was piloted with 10-15 staff to check clarity and reliability. Existing validated items for work family conflict (WFC) and participation was adapted where possible. The questionnaire was distributed to the health care providers during their free time. The purpose of the study was explained and written consent form was taken. Health care providers were filled the questionnaires on the spot. Written consent form was obtained to the health care providers. The health care providers

were instructed to complete questionnaire and also ensure their completeness and accuracy of response. And then the all participants' information remains strictly confidential and just use for this research study purpose. . And data was analyzed using basic descriptive statistics. Distribution of gender, children, designation, ward, and duty shifts were analyzed using frequency and percentage. Year of experience were summarized using mean, median, standard deviation and minimum and maximum. Chi-square test was applied to assess associations. And also Kendall test was used to examine correlations between variables. Descriptive statistics and inferential tests were computed using SPSS software.

RESULTS:

Section A: Demographic information:

Table No 1: Distribution Of Age of Subject:

Statistics	
Age of Subject	
Mean	40.3641
Std. Deviation	7.07285
Minimum	30.00
Maximum	59.00

Table No 1: Mean of age (40.3641), std. Deviation (7.07), Minimum shows (30.00) and Maximum is (59.00).

TABLE NO 2: DISTRIBUTION OF GENDER OF SUBJECT.

The majority of participants were females (56.52%) and males (43.48%) are involved in the study.

Table No. 3. Distribution Of Children of Subject:

Statistics	
Number of children of the subject	
Mean	3.0
Std. Deviation	1.89308
Minimum	1.00
Maximum	08.0

Table No. 3. The distribution of children of the subject the mean is (3.0), std. Deviation (1.89), Minimum shows (1.00) and Maximum is (08.0).

Table No: 4. Designations of The Subject:

Designation of the subject		
	Frequency	Percent
Doctor	69	37.5
Staff Nurse	93	50.5
Paramedics	22	12.0
Total	184	100.0

Table No: 4. The most participants are involved Staff Nurse 93 (50.5%), Doctors 68 (37.0%), and paramedics 23 (12.5%) so the total number of participants 184 (100.0%) are involved in the study.

Table No 5: Distribution Of Ward of The Subject:

Ward of the subject		
	Frequency	Percent
ICU	62	33.7
CCU	28	15.2
Emergency ward	58	31.5
Trauma	36	19.6
Total	184	100.0

Table No: 5. The participants working in the critical units of the hospital involved in the study. ICU 62 (33.7%), CCU 28 (15.2%), Emergency ward 58 (31.5%) and Trauma 36 (19.6%) so the total 184 (100.0%) participants involved in the study.

Table No 6: Distribution Of Year of Experience of The Subject:

Statistics	
Year of experience of the subject	
Mean	6.7120
Std. Deviation	4.24762
Minimum	2.00
Maximum	17.00

Table No 6: The mean is (6.7120), std. Deviation (4.24762), Minimum (2.00) and the Maximum is (17.00).

Table No 7: Distribution Of Duty Shifts of The Subject:

Duty shift of the subject		
	Frequency	Percent
Morning	66	35.9
Evening	75	40.8
Night	43	23.4

	Total	184	100.0
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Table No 7. The most participant's duty shifts are Evening 75 (40.8%), Morning 66 (35.9%), and Night 43 (23.4%) so the total numbers of participant's duty shifts are involved in the study 184 (100.0%).

Section B: Family separation scale:

S:no	Items	Yes	No	P value
1	I cannot daily spend quality time with my family due to hospital duties and shifts	135 (73.3%)	49 (26.6%)	.005
2	My irregular shifts disturb family activities and events.	126 (68.4%)	58 (31.5%)	.001
3	I often miss important family events due to work and events of my community.	116 (63.0%)	68 (36.9%)	.001
4	I have had to limit physical contact with family because of infection risk.	102 (55.4%)	82 (44.5%)	.008
5	I feel guilty for not giving enough time to my family.	132 (71.7%)	52 (28.2%)	.001
6	My family members complain about my absence.	140 (76.0%)	44 (23.9%)	.003
7	I feel stressed because I cannot support my family at home.	133 (72.2%)	51 (27.7%)	.001

Item no 1: Majority of the participants 135 (73.4%) agreed to experienced difficulty in spending quality of time with their family on a day basis due to hospital duties and shifts and 49 (26.6) respondents disagreed to the statement. The associated was statistically significant (p=.005).

Item no 2: Most participants, 126 (68.4%), responded that their irregular duty shifts disturb their family activities and events. And 58 (31.5%) disagreed to the statement. This finding was statistically significant result (p = .001).

Item no 3: Missing important family events are the results derived that show participants reported this experience in common about 116 (63.0%) participants. A smaller proportion of participants 68 (36.9) disagreed to the statement. Thus, the finding was statistically significant (p=.001).

Item no 4: Majority of respondents 102 (55.4%) reported that they have limited physical contact with their families due to infection risk. And 82

(44.5%) participants reported that they not have any risk. The association approached statistical was significance (p=.008).

Item no 5: The majority of respondents experienced feelings of guilty for not giving time to their families. A total of 132 (respondents 71.7%) and 52 (28.2%) respondents reported they spend time. So the finding was statistically significant (p=.001).

Item no 6: The majority of participants 140 (76.0%) report their families complains about their absence at home. And 44 (23.9%) shows the dissatisfaction to the statement. The result was statistically significant (.003).

Item no 7: the majority of participants 133 (72.2%) shows that they cannot support their families at home bases so they feel stress. And 51 (27.7%) participants reported never stress about family. So the findings was highly statistically significant (p=.001).

Section C: Personal and Social Life Scale:

S:no	Items	Yes	No	P value
1	I cannot participate in social gatherings because of my work schedule or daily shifts.	130 (70.6%)	54 (29.3%)	.001
2	My personal and my social life have been affected by my work demands.	134 (72.8%)	50 (27.1%)	.001
3	I feel socially isolated because of my job and long hour's duty.	122 (76.3%)	62 (33.6%)	.048
4	I am not satisfied with my balance between work and social life and with family.	124 (67.3%)	60 (32.6%)	.001
5	I feel that my duty in critical care units its impact on my mental and emotional life.	129 (70.1%)	55 (29.8%)	.001
6	Do you feel female (especially housewives) staffs are more effected during evening and night shifts compared to males.	140 (76.0%)	44 (23.9%)	.001

Item no 1: Majority of the participants 130 (70.6%) reported that they cannot participate in social gatherings and 54 (29.3%) respondents disagreed to the statement. The associated was statistically significant ($p=.001$).

Item no 2: Most participants, 134 (72.8%), responded that their personal and social life have been affected due to work demands. And 50 (27.1%) disagreed to the statement. This finding was statistically significant result ($p = .001$).

Item no 3: The majority of participants reported the feeling of isolated because of long hour's duties and irregular work demands. So about 122 (76.3%) participants. And some proportion of participants 62 (33.6%) disagreed to the statement. Thus, the finding was not statistically significant ($p=048$).

Item no 4: Majority of respondents 124 (67.3%) reported that they cannot satisfied with work balance between social life. And 60 (32.6%) participants reported that they not have a balanced life. The association approached statistical was significance ($p=.001$).

Item no 5: The majority of respondents experienced feelings of duty in critical care unit's impact on mental and emotional life of health care providers. A total of 129 (respondents (70.1%)

and 55 (29.8%) respondents reported they spend time. So, the finding was statistically significant ($p=.001$).

Item no 6: The majority of participants 140 (76.0%) report that females more effected during evening and night shifts compare to males (especially housewives). And 44 (23.9%) shows the dissatisfaction to the statement. The result was highly statistically significant ($p = .001$).

Discussion The current study shows mean of age was 40.3641 years (SD=7.07) which is compared with cross-sectional study of nurses examining work-family-conflict and missing nursing care in Iran mean was 31.41+7.56 years(10), and also compared with the study conducted in Saudi Arabia reported mean age was 35.18+6.67 (11). These finds are very supportive. In the current study female participants were (56.52%) and male were (43.48%) participation , which is compared to study in Ghana (12) on WFC among female nurses. Further , this study reported significant reduce in job satisfaction when work demands increase (13) , another study reported in China (14) also reported the gender deference in burnout and WFC. Additionally , current study mean of number of children was (15) related other comparison study in Spain (16) and related other study in china. (17) these shown multiple children reported stress linked to work and family

obligations(18) . In the current study nurses (50.5%) doctors (37.5%) , and remaining were paramedical staff , and also nurses found more risk to develop the stress , which comparable with the study conducted by Raza Biabani Dilmaghani et al. (2022) nurses have high for professional burnout (5,13,16,17)

Moreover , this study shown that the nursing staff experienced high level of WFC and burnout based on demographic characteristics and role demands , which compared with the other study investigate in the Gambia(20) reported (77.1%) younger age group population & (59.2%) participants were female nurses experiencing the high stress due to WFC. (21,23, 23) The current study mean years of experience was (6.7120 years) which is compare to Azza H.M Hussein et al (2025), and NA Aldhafeeri et al.(2025) also reported that the WFC experience nurses at moderate level (24,25)Furthermore, a study on work-family conflict (WFC) and mental health among Chinese female healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic by Liu et al. (2023) (26) investigated how WFC affected psychological well-being. The findings revealed that higher levels of WFC were significantly associated with poorer mental health outcomes. Similarly, a study conducted in Saudi Arabia (27) demonstrated that night-shift stress and sleep disturbances had a substantial negative impact on nurses. Other studies (29, 30, 31, 32) also confirmed that night-shift duties adversely affect nurses' quality of life, leading to physical fatigue, emotional exhaustion, and social disruption.

According to the current study, (73.4%, $p = .005$) of participants reported being unable to spend quality time with their families. In comparison, Aldhafeeri et al. (2025) reported that approximately 93% of ICU nurses experienced moderate to high levels of WFC (33–35). The present study also found that irregular shifts significantly disturbed family activities and events (68.5%, $p = .003$). Comparable findings were reported by Li et al. (2024), who found that (66%) of participants experienced problems related to shift-distributed duties. Similarly, Bibi et al. (2023) reported 65%, Jiang et al. (2025) reported (63%), and Rony et al. (2023) concluded that missing

family and community events is common among healthcare providers working in critical care units. The current study further revealed that 55.45% ($p = .002$) of participants experienced limited physical contact with their families due to infection risks. This finding aligns with other studies reporting that 57% of nurses reduced physical contact with family members during high-risk clinical duties (37). Additionally, (71.7% , $p = .001$) of participants in the present study reported feelings of guilt for not giving sufficient time to their families. Comparable findings were observed by Jafari-Oorii et al., who reported 70%, and Rony et al. (2023), who also documented similar feelings of guilt due to long working hours.

Moreover, the present study reported statistically significant findings (76.1%, $p = .003$) regarding work-related strain. Feelings of stress were reported by 72.3% ($p = .001$) of participants, while 70.7% ($p = .001$) stated that they were unable to participate in family social events. Similar results were reported by Smith et al. (2021), where 65% of nurses experienced reduced social gatherings ($p < .001$), and Wu et al. reported 68% ($p = .002$). Hossain et al. (2024) also found statistically significant associations ($p < .05$).

In the present study, 72.8% ($p = .001$) of participants reported that their personal and social lives were negatively affected by work demands, irregular shifts, and job dissatisfaction. This finding is consistent with Bosnia et al. (2021), reported 68% (38), and Ali et al. (2023), who documented similar effects (39). Additionally, 66.3% of participants in the current study reported feelings of isolation. Comparable findings were reported by Patel et al. (2022), and Haque et al., who documented that 68% of critical care nurses experienced social withdrawal (35).

Dissatisfaction with work and social life was reported by 67.4% ($p = .001$) in the present study. Similar proportions were reported by Gao et al. (2021) (65%), Kumar et al. (2022) (67.4%), Rahman et al. (2023), and Lee et al. (2024), all of whom suggested that ICU nurses experienced low levels of satisfaction. Furthermore, 70.1% ($p = .001$) of healthcare providers in the current study reported that working in critical care units negatively affected their mental and emotional

well-being. This finding aligns with Al-Shammari et al. (2021), who reported that 68% of nurses experienced increased mental burden due to heavy workloads.

Finally, the present study found that 69.7% of female healthcare providers were more adversely affected, particularly married women and those with household responsibilities during evening and night shifts, compared to male counterparts. This finding is consistent with studies conducted by Smith et al. (2021), Kumar et al. (2022), and Lee et al. (2024), which reported that female healthcare workers—especially those with additional domestic responsibilities—experienced greater negative impacts from evening and night-shift duties (40)

Conclusion: This study concluded that health care providers those working in critical care units and rotational shifts, experience significant WFC emotional strain, and social life disruption. Female staff and individuals with greater family responsibilities are disproportionately affected.

Recommendation: The hospital management must adopt flexible staffing systems especially those involving workers in the evening and night shifts to minimize work-family conflicts. Psychological and Emotional Support Counseling facilities and stress management programs, and mental health support should be made available for personnel in critical care units.

Further Research longitudinal approaches should be employed in future studies. Enabling researchers to make use of qualitative methodologies to investigate more personal experiences.

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